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**A new find of the male
Hendelia beckeri Czerny, 1903
(Diptera: Clusiidae: Clusiodinae)**

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The druid flies (Clusiidae) is a mid-sized family of > 610 species worldwide (Catalogue of Life, 2021; Systema Dipterorum, 2021) with the greatest diversity in the Neotropics (>200 species), as far as known, associated with old shady broad-leaved forests as their larvae live predominantly in rotting wood on the late stages of decomposition. Adults are slender flies with wings 2.0–6.5 mm long, often with spotted wings and patterned body, and with modified shape of head, antennae and legs of males, which demonstrate lekking and well expressed combat behavior. They are poorly represented in European collections unless reared from wood or swept at lekking localities (Lonsdale & Marshall, 2010; Marshall, 2012).

Of the eight species of Clusiidae recorded on the Fauna Europaea list from Ukraine (Merz & Roháček, 2011), only four are represented by material in the SIZK collection of Clusiidae examined and determined by Bernhard Merz in 1999: *Clusia flava* (Meigen, 1830) (Zakarpatska Region: Chynadiieve, Lumshory; Crimea: Ulu Özen = Generalske), *Clusioides albimanus* (Meigen, 1830) (Kyiv: Kontsha-Zaspa), *Clusioides pictipes* (Zetterstedt, 1855)

(Zakarpatska Region: Mukacheve, Kyiv: Lysa Hora), and *Clusioides ruficollis* (Meigen, 1830) (Zakarpatska Region: Mukacheve, Kyiv: Lysa Hora).

The reason and source for including for the two other species, *Clusioides apicalis* (Zetterstedt, 1848) and *Hendelia beckeri* Czerny, 1903 remain unknown to us.

While collecting flies on sap of a bleeding tree in the oak woods, the authors have noted and collected a single male of one of the species on list not confirmed by far from Ukraine.

***Hendelia beckeri* Czerny, 1903 (figs 1–4)**

Material. Ukraine: Irpin / Romanivske bog, bleeding oak, on sap, 50.501°N, 30.275°E, 09.05.2018, 1 ♂ (S. & V. Korneyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. All European countries, except Iceland, Ireland and South (Merz & Roháček, 2011).

Remarks. This species can be easily recognized from the enlarged trapezoid flagellomere one and thickened, black, densely pubescent arista, combined with the body and wing pattern.

Figs 1–4. *Hendelia beckeri* ♂: 1 — habitus, lateral view; 2 — head, antero-lateral view; 3 — wing; 4 — mesonotum, dorsal view.

References

Catalogue of Life. 2021. Accessed on <https://www.catalogueoflife.org/data/taxon/8CL> 29.09.2021.
Lonsdale, O. & Marshall, S. A. 2010. 78. Clusiidae (clusiid flies). In: Brown, B. V., Borkent, A., Wood, D. M. & Zumbado, M., eds. *Manual of Central American Diptera*, Vol. 2. Ottawa, NRC: 1041–1048.

Marshall, S. L. 2012. *Flies. The natural history and diversity of Diptera*. Buffalo & Richmond Hills, Firefly Books: 1–616.
Merz, B. & Roháček, J. 2011. Fauna Europaea: Tephritidae. Fauna Europaea version 2.4. Accessed on <https://fauna-eu.org> 29.09.2021.
Systema Dipterorum. 2021. Version 3.3. Accessed on <https://fauna-eu.org> 29.09.2021.

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